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From Drama to Game-Based Television: Re-mystifying 'God' in *The Gods Are Not to Blame* and *Big Brother Naija*"

Abstract

This paper presents a cross-disciplinary discourse of the concept and functionality of 'god' from drama and theatre to game-based television shows. Despite attempts by some Western philosophical traditions to dismiss the presence of the divine in human affairs, the idea of 'god' remains central to contemporary entertainment culture. A variety of television entertainment programmes like drama, soap operas, season serial dramas, sports, and game-based television shows have continued to redesign and present 'god' in various forms. Using the 'Big Brother Naija' reality TV show and Ola Rotimi's *The Gods Are Not to Blame* (henceforth BBN and *The Gods*), this paper examines how god-like figures are re-imagined through different media. Through discourse analyses of *The Gods* and 'Big Brother Naija', the characteristics of a re-mystified god in drama and game-based TV shows in Nigeria are examined. It is concluded that the idea of 'god' will continue to be represented in different artistic genres for contemporary audience, particularly through technological innovations in media content productions.

Keywords: Game/reality TV, Drama, Television, God, Technology

Introduction

In *The Gay Science* (1882) and later in *Thus Spoke Zarathustra* (1883) Friedrich Nietzsche proclaimed the death of God. In the nineteenth century may not have only sounded as apostasy to religious people; it would also be considered extremist by theists. Nietzsche's position did not come as a shock to many pro-God philosophers and theologians, it was rather a continuous manifestation of his atheist predecessors' philosophical idiosyncrasy. This statement came at the height of the Enlightenment when rational philosophy was overshadowing the relevance of God in Western society, and in Christendom in particular. At that point, the claim of the Church as playing a mediational role between the divine body and humanity was considered fraudulent (Barnett, 2). But notable philosophers like Kant, Hegel and Descartes reiterated the existence and indispensability of God, even in the face of the

rapidly emerging modernity in their time. But for all his acerbic polemics about God, Nietzsche yet expressed the possibilities of traces of God in the affairs of men for years to come, because though: "God is dead; but given the way of men, there may still be caves for thousands of years in which his shadow will be shown" (167).

The essence of this constant appearance of the figure of God among humans is thus underpinned in the need for morality and order in a world where there is perpetual tendency for injustice, conflict, and chaos. The various histories of social conflicts and wars from the pre-modern to the postmodern era are an attestation to the fact that there continues to exist a struggle between the binary class composition of the human global structure: or simply put, a struggle between the Other and the Centre, the rich and the poor, the weak and the strong among other binary configurations of injustice as argued by Karl Marx over a century ago.

Generally, the perceived meaning of social injustice is a situation in a state where unfair practices reign supreme because they go against the laws and moral standards of the state, thereby setting a sharp imbalance and conflict between the politically powerful and the masses (Siddiqui, 254). Social psychologists have noted that such imbalance causes tension which manifests in different shades such as racism, religious domination, economic domination and control, tribalism, sexism among other forms of social inequalities.

Checking the excesses of leadership and followership therefore calls for the entrenchment of law and order which largely anchor on morality, and which Plato considers as either gods-bestowed or gods-endorsed for the society. Beyond the function of moral willingness or imposition, this paper attempts to identify other functionalities of god in drama as a social mirror, and how such dispositions have been replicated or re-imagined for game-based television formats.

However, outside religion and the philosophical discourse of God where the concept of the divine is the epicentre of the rhetoric of theology, poetry, drama and theatre rank among the first art genre where the functionality and the place of god in human affairs were presented in an entertainment form. The evolution history of traditional cultural festivals and rituals from Africa to the Oriental and Occidental worlds have connected these communal festivities to the gods and other supernatural bodies, and such performances have been described by scholars in dramatic and theatrical terms.

Furthermore, the formalisation of dramatic and theatrical performances in fifth-century Athens also underscores the centrality of the gods or god-like characters in Greek tragedy, which either evolved from the worship and celebration of god Dionysus, or which Scullion opined was at best "associated with the patron god [Dionysus] of tragedy at Athens" (31). But as much as the plays were the peak of communal celebration of Dionysus, the performances did not

only function as circular entertainment with religious roots: importantly too, the plots and conflicts of most of the plays were kings and gods connected; and this was partly because the plays were set in the distant "past, the heroic age, when men had walked with gods" (Sourvinou-Inwood, 7).

The style of presenting god through cultural *magicality* or magical realism, as in aboriginal or culture-based drama and theatre, has since grown from natural mysticism; the concept and style of presenting god is taking on new dimensions and forms for different media with the aid of artistic thoughts in alignment with technology. The ubiquitous characteristic and conception of god keeps resurfacing in novel forms on modern media platforms as shown in diverse media programming concepts and formats. This paper discusses some of the novel ways in which the supernatural characteristic and functionalities of god, as commonly found in culture-based drama, is being re-imagined in pop culture entertainment, and how these features yet epitomise god-functionality, specifically in game-based television formats.

With Nigeria in context, the paper anchors on Ola Rotimi's *The Gods* as the source of the gods presence in Nigerian formal drama and theatre practice: this hinges on its canonical nature as though an appropriated drama, but which has also been a source-text to a plethora of Nigerian tragedies, for both the stage, film, and television. *The Gods* is used to reveal how the transcendental characteristic of god or the supernatural is re-imagined from theatre-text to game-based television platform as exemplified in BBN.

II. Connecting *The Gods* and BBN

The basis for the cross-disciplinary discourse analysis of 'god' in *The Gods* and BBN is hinged on some factors congenial to both works. Separate from the artistic genre they share, *The Gods* and BBN directly and indirectly possess the 'god' element first in their invisibility as god; and second by virtue of the influential power viz. charting the trajectory of their 'creatures' as evident in both works.

Synoptically, *The Gods* and BBN present the classical god-man pattern whereby the supernatural plays the role of 'the author and finisher' of man's destiny; or where, at least, the gods wield some preternatural control over the being of man. Ola Rotimi's *The Gods* presents the story of a boy who the gods fated to commit incest and patricide for no obvious reasons neither known to the protagonist, Odewale, nor the entire people; the unfortunate ill-fated victim would live in agony and penance of self-enucleation and roam the earth to an unknown destination for the rest of his life.

In BBN, individuals with different socio-economic backgrounds, temperaments, and abilities are converged under the same roof for usually a quarter of a year. For this period, the unseen

and god-like figure, known as Big Brother, controls the physical, psychological, and emotional levels of the housemates by giving tasks and punishing or rewarding housemates according to their successes, abilities, and behaviours. Importantly too, a housemate's popularity as submitted through public voting, conducted and perhaps influenced by Big Brother, also determines whom Big Brother declares the winner.

Further, *The Gods* and BBN have some connections to the Greek world. On the one hand, *The Gods* is an appropriation of Sophocles' *Oedipus Rex*, a classical tragedy which influenced and defined Aristotle's classical theory of tragedy which has remained central to academic discourse of tragedy world over. Similarly, the Big Brother format was originally created in the Netherlands and "The Dutch original aired [it] in spring 2000" (Wong, 35). The format was syndicated into the Nigerian tele-space as Big Brother Nigeria (but currently Big Brother Naija) in 2016.

Meanwhile, the one eye symbol of BBN indicates some, perhaps, peripheral connection between the general Big Brother format and the Hellenic world. The cyclopic logo of BBN is reminiscent of the cyclops phenomenon in Greek mythology. The Cyclopes featured prominently in *Theogony* where Hesiod explains that they (Cyclopes) are a group of three children, out of all the offspring of the Earth, who were peculiar for having one eye in their foreheads; and who gave Zeus his power of lightning, thunder, and bright (Hesiod, 13-15). Similarly, Euripides' play, *Cyclops*—a play about the encounter of Odysseus with the man-eating Cyclops, is appropriated from Homer's *Odyssey* (Dougherty, 313).

Significantly, Wong, drawing on Foucault's idea of a unified surveillance through an all-seeing eye referred to as panopticons, iterates that the panoptical characteristic of Big Brother, as reflected in the Cyclopic logo, is rooted in Jeremy Bentham's panopticon which is a:

...late eighteenth century ... series of writings on prison reform. In the panopticon, inmates are housed in a structure in which their every movement can, in principle, be continuously observed. Bentham thought that such an arrangement would induce the prisoners to improve their behaviour (37).

Meanwhile, the Big Brother title and concept is significantly linked to and adapted from Orwellian anti-totalitarian leadership literary corpus. The concept is derived from George Orwell's *Nineteen Eighty-Four* where all the movements and actions of the citizens of the state are under total watch by the totalitarian government.

Thus, the literary evolution of the Big Brother format establishes a concrete connection between drama and, by extension, theatre and television; it as well underlines the cross-discourse relevance of *The Gods* and BBN—especially how the former as a theatre platform, has generally impacted on the culture of postmodern popular media content and style. The

following section focuses on the discourse of one of such areas of impact viz. the element of the supernatural concept of god and its metamorphosis from the all-knowing fate-bestower in *The Gods* to the all-seeing and all-hearing benevolent cum malevolent Big Brother in BBN; the manners in which the concept of god is re-imagined in game-based television formats are identified and discussed.

II. The mysticism of god: From *The Gods*...

The source of inspiration for this paper is the centrality of the phenomenon of god(s) in *The Gods*. Therefore, a discourse of the mysticism of god, as presented here, is approached by first explaining the status quo, concept, relationship, and functionality of god—that is god as ritually-imagined in culture-based drama—in relation to characters in drama: the example of the characters in *The Gods*, who imaginatively accept the lordly pre-eminence status of god as key to defining their essence, is cited.

Panoptics is rooted in Foucault's idea of biopolitics and biopower where modern system of governance takes total administrative control of the lives of its citizens, including putting all their activities under surveillance.

Secondly, the discourse is furthered by explicating, through established conceptualised concepts, the metamorphosis of god as ritual imagination in culture-based plays, as in *The Gods*, to the *supartificial* re-imagination of god in BBN. The supartificial technique is examined under the ideas of human-mediated god and human-technology-facilitated god. The ensuing analyses are aided by underlining the artistic aim behind the works, the supernatural capabilities, and functionalities of god in relation to the content and characters of the texts.

a. What makes god 'god': The ritually imagined god in *The Gods* and its acceptance

Ritually imagined god explains the mythological and artistic (re)creation of a phenomenon whose intelligibility transcends the physical milieu of a work, and which the audience is ready to accept by willingly suspending its disbelief. Ritual imagination is essentially the cultural thinking in the collective consciousness of a people on the primacy of the supernatural, myth, mysteries, ethics, taboos, and the gods over the mundane. It is also a "faculty of mental images that suggests a peculiar worldview" (Balogun 7). Eghagha also defines ritual imagination as "the socio-cultural orientation found in the micro-cosmos that is presented in a play which views all actions as transcendental phenomena" (qtd. in Balogun, 7).

The ritually imagined god is thus an author's re-shaping of a culture as influenced by his cultural orientation and artistic vision cum style. Such preternatural phenomenon is

respectively grounded in the cosmological belief of a people/characters as defined without and within the fictional ambience of a text.

Explicitly, ritually-imagined gods in drama evolve from the cultural consciousness of writers as culture products. These are stories of culturally established gods and deities that define the relationship and interactions between the quotidian and the supernatural cosmological levels, especially how the latter transcends the former. These stories are recreated through the process of myth recreation, otherwise known as mythopoeia. Ogunyemi's *Obaluaye*, Osofisan's *Esu and the Vagabond Minstrels*, Yerima's *Ade Ire* and *Yemoja*, Balogun's *Oya* and *Moremi Ajaasoro* among a plethora of god-related oeuvres in Greek classical drama and other cultures, are regarded as ritually-imagined gods in drama.

Writers, through the dramatic presentation of the exploits of legendary characters, hero-turned-demigods, and extraordinary fictional characters, also create godlike characters. Legendary and heroic characters like Shaka Zulu in Mulikita's *Shaka Zulu*, Didan Kimathi and Woman in *The Trials of Dedan Kimathi*, Olunde in *Death and the King's Horseman*, Princess Adebisi in *For Heroes and Scoundrels*, and Antigone in *Antigone* possess godlike capabilities through sagacity, selflessness, and the valour they showed in either changing the status quo, challenging unpopular leadership, and or saving their communities.

Antigone has mostly been praised for her godlike valour:

Antigone's disobedience of the edict of Creon, the King of Thebes, and her burial of her brother Polynices in defiance of that edict, have been seen by many modern readers as a noble act by a courageous individual rebelling against a tyrannical state, Antigone being perceived as a heroic figure who did her familial duty and obeyed the gods, privileging family and divine law over the law of an oppressive tyrant. (Sourvinou-Inwood, 7).

Some playwrights give fictionally or historically-inspired autocratic and villainous characters some god or supernatural energies akin to that of mythical gods: Efunsetan Aniwura, Mojagbe, Odibei, and Creon are some legendary antagonists who are extremely villainous by dispensing the intimidating power of the gods on their victims.

Further, the origin of the gods in *The Gods* is rooted in Yoruba cosmological myth and belief in the existence of the supernatural. The Yoruba cultural belief in *The Gods* reflects in the characters' practical worship and reverencing act of the pantheons, who they (the characters) accept as their source.

Traditionally, the gods are headed by the Supremo God, Eledumare or Eleda—the creator, the bestower of mortals' fates or the giver of essence; while other gods are paths through which mortals tread to locate, connect and lead a fulfilling life, or fulfil a doomed destiny. Thus, the

all-in-all attribute of the gods automatically command a reverencing duty from men who are like their children. However, the father-children relationship, as evident in the mutual benefaction from both entities, does not guarantee that the latter's reverencing and worshiping acts of his father will ensure that he fulfils a blissful essence. This is because the gods, rather than be like a father figure to their children, have instead "turn[ed] to oppress the helpless immortals" (Ayebona, 4). The reason for the oppression is because the anthropomorphic gods struggle amongst themselves to control the world and man; so they are easily disposed to competitiveness and jealousy; hence causing them to often change their minds by most times making unfavourable things happen to man through their arbitrary will (McKirahan, 7). However, this thought of oppressive proclivity of the gods seems the antithesis of Rotimi's artistic motivation and aim as clearly read in the title—*The Gods Are Not to Blame*.

Regardless of the oppressive tendency as highlighted, the natural belief in the supremacy of the gods remains a common 'article of faith' among the diverse communities and people who are actively or passively presented in *The Gods*. The people of Kutuje and neighbouring communities like Ikolu, Atakumosa, Ishokun, and Ijekun Yemoja—where Odewale erroneously believed to be his hometown—therefore share a congenial credo in the gods.

Importantly, the imaginative acceptance of the supremacy of the gods by the people of Kutuje, especially in all matters concerning their existence, is demonstrated in a number of ways. The people readily believe in fate and the fact that it is bestowed by the gods; they believe in the system of revealing newborns' fates as a tradition to be done after the birth of a baby i.e. through the oracle and the soothsayer; and in spite of the angst of baby Odewale's parents, and the general helpless situation the people find themselves regarding the god horribly fating an innocent boy, yet the people accept the "kill the boy!" order of the gods as the only way out of the impending sacrilege. But no one better demonstrates the collective acceptance of the centrality of the gods than the leader of the people—King Odewale himself:

Before Ogun the God of Iron, I stand on oath. Witness now all you present that before the feast of Ogun, which starts at sunrise, I, Odewale, the son of Ogundele, shall search and fully lay open before your very eyes the murderer of king Adetusa. And having seized that murderer, I swear by this sacred arm of Ogun, that I shall straightway bring him to the agony of slow death. First, he shall be exposed to the eyes of the world and put to shame—the beginning of living death. Next, he shall be put into lasting darkness, his eyes tortured in the living sockets until their blood and rheum swell forth to fill the hollow of crushed eyeballs. And then, the final agony: we shall cut him from his roots. Expelled from this land of his birth, he shall roam in darkness in the land of nowhere, and there die unmourned by men who know him not.... May the gods of our fathers—

Obatala, Orunmila, Shango, Sopono, Esu-Elegbara, Agemo, Ogun—stand by me (24).

King Odewale's act, as highlighted above, is the height of the imaginative or 'natural' acceptance of the gods by not just Odewale who understands the cultural import of invoking Ogun and the support of other pantheons in promising justice against the unknown offender; rather, it shows the people's general belief in other gods, as expressed by their leader, other than the fate bestowing god. Thus, separate from the sociological (re)presentation of *The Gods*, which Rotimi himself had claimed, the drama formally presents that 'unquestionable' capability of the gods, the fate determining, the all-knowing, the all-seeing, the dispenser of justice, the inexplicably intimidating, and the general lordship status of the gods over Odewale, the heroic protagonist in the drama, and the people in general: some of these attributes of god are also demonstrated in BBN as will be subsequently seen.

More so, like the characters in *The Gods*, the housemates in BBN also readily understand and accept the rules of engagement as designed by Big Brother ones they were admitted into the house as co-contestants on the show. Thus, they understand their roles as not just contestants, but also as human subjects whose fates are largely dictated by the god-like character, Big Brother, or Biggie as foundly called by the housemates.

III. Re-imagining 'god' in game-based television: the human-technology hybrid

The re-imagination of god in game-based television formats is generally anchored on the amalgamation of human and technological factors. This eclecticism, which is here conceptualised as *supartificial re-imagination* of god, is achieved with the integration of human efforts and specific technologies (especially media technologies) in consciously, or otherwise, moulding god-like image and attributes out of man and machine with the goal of attaining fairness or perfection. Implicitly, god-like characters are conceived as organic parts of game-based television formats—including reality TV shows, TV game-shows, sports show among others. In these shows, the unique point, or the spine of a show's concept, reflects some kind of effects which may be described as 'transcendental'.

The human effort in this regard manifests in two ways. First is the rigorous cerebral activity of evolving and designing a television game-based format. Secondly, the unique point of a format could be built around a mystified individual with the likeliness of god: like the Banker in Deal or No Deal, Big Brother in the Big Brother format, as well as the numerous judges in different talent hunt shows; it is also pertinent to mention that the referees and umpires in sporting activities could pass as humans who have god-like attributes.

Moreover, science and technology is essential to creating concepts or a god-like character as Big Brother in game-based television shows. In fact, new technologies have often times sparked off the conceptualisation of new television formats as iterated by Biressi and Nunn:

Over the longer term, new and newly adapted technologies have frequently been the trigger for the development of new documentary styles. Since the 1960s the relative portability of hand-held cameras, changes in sound recording, the availability of home movie equipment, video and CCTV, the possibility of live web-streaming and DV cameras all appeared to liberate filmmakers, allowing them to represent reality all the more convincingly (15-16).

Thus, against the background of the diverse traditional means in which the attributes of god have been presented through the medium of drama—namely the ritual imaginative belief in/acceptance of the gods, the oracular revelation, the authorised verbal disclosure, and through anthropomorphic theism—game-based television formats have however leveraged media technologies and innovations to re-imagine god technologically. In what Drotner calls "convergent media" (18), CCTV cameras, large digital screens, voice recognising computers, mobile phones, buzzers among other ICT technologies are integrated as organic part of an entire artistic conception and design of television game-based formats.

The footballing world recently witnessed the introduction of such technologies as the Goal Line Technology and the Video Assistant Referee (VAR) in facilitating perfect officiating and decision-making on the field of play: this, many commentators have considered as the answer to refereeing problems (Garland et al., 210). Media technologies or simple design elements are often integrated with human factors to re-imagine and present the idea of god with the aim of achieving the right decision, making perfect calls, or in projecting other god characteristics. In the following section, the hybridisation of man and technology in re-imagining god in BBN is discussed as *supartificial* re-imagination.

IV. Supartificial re-imagination of god in BBN

The supartificial re-imagination of god in BBN is the interplay of human-technology as evident in the god-like Big Brother character. The BBN format is significantly anchored on the use of CCTV cameras along with audio enhancing fixtures and human efforts to do a documentation of the activities of the contestants on the show. The concept of the reality game-show hinges on total surveillance of the housemates by infinitely keeping eyes on all the personal actions as well as the interpersonal engagements of the housemates through camera lenses.

This 'all eyes on you' feature of BBN is otherwise known as the fly-on-the-wall technique in video production. Fly-on-the-wall docu-technique is based on keen and detailed observation of events, people, and institutions with the expectations that the observed suspends his/her disbelief about the indirect presence of the observer at the time of recording. What the unphysical presence of the observer does is that it spurs the talents to develop natural extemporisation on their part, and this enhances believability of the broadcast actions on the part of the audience (Kilborn, 43).

Therefore, like the gods in *The Gods* see Odewale's horrendous fate before birth and as well watch him grow to execute his bad destiny, and in the process degenerate his heroic status to that of a tragic hero, so is Big Brother an all-seeing and all-knowing phenomenon who probably knows the winner before the show commences for a season. In BBN, the hidden cameras enable the eponymous god-figure, Big Brother, maintain a panoptic watch on the housemates as they perform their daily activities in the house.

The CCTV 'eyes' of Biggie, which is similar to the Cyclops or the eye on the line in tennis games, (Garland et al, 211) follows the contestants around the different apartments and corners of the house: from the housemates' apartments in the morning, to the physical exercises arena; from the lounge to the kitchen; from the game arena, to the club on weekends; and the camera lenses remain on them all through the night in bed. Big Brother literally sees his 'creatures' by penetrating into the private core of the housemates with his eagle vision. His ubiquitously digital eyes allow no hidden place for the housemates to engage in any clandestine affairs. Due to its complete watch on the contestants, Big Brother has had to release some footages of sexual escapades between some housemates in past seasons of the show—for example sexual escapes between Tin Tall Tony and Bisola, and Gedoni and Khafi in the third and fourth seasons of the show respectively.

More so, Big Brother tracks the verbal conversations of his 'creatures' through the mini microphones attached to each housemate. This facilitates him to be abreast of all verbal exchanges between the housemates, so as to understand the relationship between two housemates, or a group of them. In the season 4, Pepper Dem edition, when Big Brother asked if Mercy is considering any of the male folks in the house for a possible relationship, she responded "Yes Ike, but I want to slow it down for now because I've been through a lot in my past relationships. But he is one guy i'll love to be with after the house"(PM News).

The vocal augmentation is also a way of understanding the psyche and thought pattern of each housemate; because through his supartificial attributes, *Biggie* knows that 'it is from the abundance of the heart that the mouths of his creatures speaketh'. Big Brother always orders the housemates to either 'check' or 'readjust' their mic, because vocalisation must not be kept clandestine from his lordship. This is clearly stated in the D section of the Rule Book:

The Housemates are filmed 24/7 and they must have their microphones on at all times. The viewers [and Big Brother] must be able to hear all conversations at all times and are not allowed to whisper or cover their mouths while speaking to fellow Housemates. They are also not allowed to reveal the location of the cameras and microphones (Ez).

Consequently, like the gods in *The Gods*, Big Brother constitutes an all-seeing and all-hearing god who, in his omniscient capacity, is aware of the mundane activities of his 'creatures' as aided by integrated media technologies.

But Biggie is also 'transcendental' in his capacity. He is not only able to read the minds of his 'creatures' through their verbal and physical actions; rather, he knows and is privy to the thoughts and mind-workings of individual housemates during the diary session:

Diary Sessions are one of the most important aspects of the show's success and are compulsory. Once a Housemate is called to the Diary Room, they must drop everything they are doing and proceed to the Diary Room.... Housemates can request to enter the Diary Room at any time of the day or night. *Sunglasses and hats are not permitted in the Diary Room. The door for the Diary Room will be locked when not in use and no one is allowed into the room if it is occupied* [emphasis added] (Ez).

Albeit, the diary session allows the housemates to totally unmute their feelings and opinions about themselves, the other housemates, and about the benefaction or otherwise of Biggie himself; however, the disavowal of hats and sunglasses in the diary room may be read as an attempt by Biggie to gain some insights into the inner-minds of his 'creatures'. He complements and matches the verbal responses given by the housemates during the diary session with other nonverbal undertones which are required in a strategic fact-finding mission; this thus sets him on the pedestal of an all-knower—a god who has an absolute knowledge about his housemates. The fact-finding strategy is important for Biggie to have the knowledge of the inner thoughts of the housemates, hence uncovering the reason for some of their actions towards other housemates on the show. By way of implication, Biggie, like the gods in *The Gods*, becomes aware of each housemate's sensibilities of love or hate towards the others; albeit, the housemates are also allowed to make requests for personal wants from his benevolent lordship.

Biggie's omniscience is rehashed in the voice recognising computer in 'Who Wants To Be A Millionaire?'. At the point on the show when a contestant opts to use the 50-50 lifeline, the presenter would ask the computer to delete two incorrect answers, and leave one correct and one incorrect answer, out of which the contestant then chooses. The voice recognising

computer does not merely demonstrate some kind of omniscient in this regard by knowing which options are right or wrong (though as already programmed on it), it rather points to a unique man-god integration and interaction as a constant idea as embedded in the supartificial conceptualisation of game-based television formats; this will also be seen in subsequent analysis.

Nevertheless, while the intangible imaginative acceptance of the gods by the characters in *The Gods* is strongly founded on the collectively constructed material and nonmaterial culture; the existing god in BBN is rather aided through technological materials, though tangibly accepted by the contestants as a huge influence on their lives on the show, and respected by the audiences who understand that Biggie dictates the show. The oracular revelatory role as mediated through a proficient and ordained soothsayer, like the blind Baba Fakunle in *The Gods*, is demystified and countered with the direct communicative privilege which the housemates have with Biggie—though the time for conversation is determined by the latter. The same man-god communication is however re-mystified in the employment of cameras and audio-enhancing fixtures in BBN.

Implicitly, the introductory phrase, "This is Big Brother", usually said by Biggie to call attention, order, or make an announcement to the housemates, underscores the human aspect of the human-technology technique of re-imagining god in BBN. The human voice cum its audio technology enhancement become organic to the entire BBN reality show concept; it facilitates in breaking the communicative barrier that would naturally exist between the mundane man and the spiritual god. Apart from announcing his presence and giving orders through his robust baritone voice, Biggie uses the voice communication to register and remind of his lordship existence on the consciousness of the housemates.

Therefore, the combination of the human-technology technique results in creating a god with a contrasting but complementary traits: albeit Biggie's figure is mystified, but his voice is audible to both the housemates and viewers, hence making 'the voice of man become the voice of god'. The contrasting mix of natural and supernatural undertones further reflect some unusual man-god connect in BBN, which is at variance with mortal-supernatural interaction in culture-based drama where there is clear distinction between the terrestrial and celestial levels. For instance, except generally through effigy or other material representation, the characters in *The Gods* neither physically see the gods that fated Odewale, nor did they audibly hear him speak directly to them; they are only able to communicate with the gods through a skilled human medium. Conversely, the housemates need no soothsayer in Baba Fakunle to communicate with 'god' Biggie: they hear his voice, and directly air their opinions and feelings in the diary room when they are summoned by Biggie.

More so, the technique of hybridisation is made to achieve a more technical status in the Ninjas who are specially costumed in Ninja-typical apparels. The Ninjas are like angels who, similar to god Biggie, should be invincible. Albeit, the physical figure of the Ninjas is seen, but their facial identities remain unknown to the housemates and viewers owing to their masked faces. Interpretatively, the undisclosed faces of the Ninjas gives them a pseudo-transcendental essence.

Like Biggie and his Ninjas, the Banker in Deal or No Deal is, for instance, not only enshrouded in some mysticism as apparent in his/her silhouetted image cum his/her muted voice; his/her capacity of determining a contestant's fate in the game-playing process makes him/her worthy as a *supartificial* god. Previous conception of the Banker on the show solely emphasised the human element, but mobile phone has been introduced into current episodes to facilitate the secrete communication offer for the contestant between the anchor and the Banker. This further signifies the human-technology makeup of god in game-based television formats.

Conclusion

The Gods is not just canonical because it continues to inspire critical attention and artistic re-appropriation; it importantly establishes and reflects the creator-creature relationship between the natural and the supernatural, or in other words, between man and God or the gods, especially in the age when philosophical existentialists' traits are reverberated in technologies. However, against the ideological wish of anti-god champions, the twentieth and the twenty-first centuries have indirectly brought humans closer to the concept of god, rather than severing the man-supernatural connection. It is ironical that while anti-god philosophy like existentialism and people like Nietzsche have attempted to demystify God or the gods by denying their involvement with man's affairs, man has himself reawaken and continue to popularise the concept of God and the gods in the world of technologically-driven entertainment concepts. Indeed, it is for a fact that the idea of god, which finds its entertainment representational root in drama and theatre, has continued to be manifested and reimagined in game-based television formats in a country like Nigeria where God and religion are key aspect of the people's culture. Save for religion, theatre and drama like *The Gods* and other culture-based drama are sources to the cultural concept of God and the gods; and such have been re-imagined through diverse entertainment concepts and formats. Essentially, game-based television formats are using the combination of human and technology in achieving the idea of supernatural effect. Computers, infotech technologies, and the incorporation of other multimedia technologies are significant to the re-mystification of God and gods in game-based television formats. Thus, as long as entertainment concepts like television game-shows and reality television shows are enacted, balance, fairness, and

perfection will always be the watchword, hence the need for a *supartificially* imagined god-like image.

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